

Supplementary File of “Coupling Forward and Inverse Transfer for Expensive Multiobjective Optimization”

S-I. BENCHMARK PROBLEMS

The selected DTLZ problems are constructed based on objective functions with distance functions. The objective functions can be illustrated as follows:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} f_1 = \frac{1}{2}x_1^s x_2^s \dots x_{M-1}^s [1 + g(\mathbf{x}_M)] \\ f_2 = \frac{1}{2}x_1^s x_2^s \dots (1 - x_{M-1}^s) [1 + g(\mathbf{x}_M)] \\ \vdots \\ f_M = \frac{1}{2}(1 - x_1^s) [1 + g(\mathbf{x}_M)] \\ x_i \in [0, 1], i = 1, 2, \dots, D \end{array} \right. \quad (\text{S-1})$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} f_1 = [1 + g(\mathbf{x}_M)] \cos(x_1^s \pi/2) \dots \cos(x_{M-1}^s \pi/2) \\ f_2 = [1 + g(\mathbf{x}_M)] \cos(x_1^s \pi/2) \dots \sin(x_{M-1}^s \pi/2) \\ \vdots \\ f_M = [1 + g(\mathbf{x}_M)] \sin(x_1^s \pi/2) \\ x_i \in [0, 1], i = 1, 2, \dots, D \end{array} \right. \quad (\text{S-2})$$

where M is the number of objectives, D is the number of dimensions, and $g(x)$ function is the distance function defined as follow:

$$g(\mathbf{x}_M) = g_a * (|\mathbf{x}_M| + \sum_{x_i \in \mathbf{x}_M} [(x_i - p_i)^2 - g_b * \cos(g_c \pi (x_i - p_i))]) \quad (\text{S-3})$$

$$g(\mathbf{x}_M) = \sum_{x_i \in \mathbf{x}_M} (x_i - p_i)^2 \quad (\text{S-4})$$

To be specific, DTLZ-1 is constructed by the objective function (S-1) and the distance function (S-3), DTLZ-2 is constructed by the objective function (S-2) and the distance function (S-4), and DTLZ-3 is constructed by the objective function (S-2) and the distance function (S-3). For the selected DTLZ problems in the original version, in distance function (S-3) the parameter set (g_a, g_b, g_c) equals $(100, 1, 20)$, while the parameter set is set as $(1, 1, 2)$ for mDTLZ-1 and $(0.1, 0.1, 2)$ for mDTLZ-3. The parameters utilized to shift the base mDTLZ problem to build multiple related mDTLZ problem sets are shown in Table S-I.

TABLE S-I
PARAMETER SETTINGS OF THE MDTLZ BENCHMARK PROBLEMS.

Task Index	Task Index	s	p_1	p_2	p_3	p_4
mDTLZ1	Task-1	0.35	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
	Task-2	0.30	0.25	0.50	0.75	1.00
	Task-3	0.25	0.125	0.25	0.375	0.50
	Task-4	0.20	0.083	0.167	0.25	0.33
mDTLZ2	Task-1	1.0	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
	Task-2	0.75	0.25	0.50	0.75	1.00
	Task-3	0.50	0.125	0.25	0.375	0.50
	Task-4	0.25	0.083	0.167	0.25	0.33
mDTLZ3	Task-1	0.20	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
	Task-2	0.18	0.25	0.50	0.75	1.00
	Task-3	0.16	0.125	0.25	0.375	0.50
	Task-4	0.14	0.083	0.167	0.25	0.33